

Apologizing in English and Indonesian : An Interlanguage Pracmatic Case Study of Students at Muhammadiyah Boarding School Rappang

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ABSTRACT

This research uses the qualitative method as the research methodology. This research was conducted to know what How are students ability to apologize and How are the apology strategies of students at the Islamic boarding school. The population in this research were the students of Muhammadiyah boarding school Rappang in this research were 6 students dan 2 Teachers. The data collection method used in this research was an interview. The results showed that most of the Muhammadiyah boarding school Rappang students apologized by addressing the person directly. and they have different strategies in apologizing. Several strategies to apologize to friends that can be done are Express an apology directly, apologize by giving an explanation, apologize by saying responsibility, apologize by offering a fix, and apologize by promising not to do it again.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a very important role in human life and is very supportive of continuity in communication. Language is not only tool or means to convey information. But language is also used to operating all activities of human life. Language also a media interaction among fellow and means delivery knowledge. Such as study, conseling, news, and even for conveying a thought. Language is the main tool in communication and has powerful in expression and informative. Language needed by man, because with language man can fulfill than needs. They use to communicate among one with other. As a member public active in life humans are very depended on the use of language. Thing this by the statement that "where there is society there is the use of language". With words other, in where activity occurs. In there, activity speak occur also in Jatmiko (1992:2).

One of elements that make apology an critical aspect of successful communique, so long as restraining relationship is involved, is its relation with politeness and face. Each apology and politeness are accomplished with the aid of an audio system so that you can mitigate the ugly impact of face- threatening acts as well as reveal the attention to another individual's face to turbines (2003). Moreover, an apology as noted by Coates and Cameron (1998), is directed to the addressee's negative face. It is a politeness approach that has the effect of being attentive to the addressee's face using acknowledging a capability imposition in apologizing speakers observe a wide range of apology techniques. Those techniques which can vary from one person to another are methods by which the audio system carries out the speech act of apology, supporting them to effectively carry out the apologizing acts and preserve the connection between the apologizer and the angry man or women. Other apology techniques, there are various factors including the severity of the infraction or the context in which the offense happens that motivate the audio systems to choose a specific sort of apology method. Based on the reason above, the researcher will conduct research on "Apologizing In English and Indonesian : An interlanguage Pracmatic case study of students at Muhammadiyah Boarding school Rappang.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The word that should be said after making a mistake is "sorry". Naturally, when you realize that you have made a mistake, even though it is difficult to say, it is still necessary to apologize to someone who has "accidentally" been hurt. However, even if it's only one word, why is it so hurd to say? Because in general, we prioritize, and because of the pride that is within ourselves. For example, because they feel they have much higher position, or because they feel richer, smarter, or older.

According to Searle (Laksita, 2010:13), the expression sorry goes into the category of expressive with the assumption that the speaker expresses or expresses his feelings in this case, the speaker expresses the feeling of not feeling good or guilty for doing an action that hurts people's feelings other (partner speech) and with ask to excuse me convey regret which felt speaker to partner said. (Douglas 2006:83) in (Laksita, 2010:15). This is an important social

ritual. Way to show respect and empathy to the aggrieved person. On the other hand, not giving Request sincere apologies it means somebody shows no respect for the person or people who have injured. An apology is not just a form of making amends, but something we do to apologize. Be a way to show respect and empathy for the angry person. On the other hand, by not offering a sincere apology, we are showing disrespect towards the person or people we have offended. In addition to expressing respect and empathy, there are several other reasons why apologizing to those we have hurt or offended is so important:

That's a reason why apologies Becomes an important thing for conduct when You make an error. So, ask sorry when now You have an error yet resolved. We understand the need to apologize when we have hurt a friend or other person, whether intentionally or unintentionally. As for the benefits of apologizing when we live in society Apologize Becomes a method so the problem happened no tail long and makes a heart as well as thought relieved. Although so, delivering apologize after To do an error or can hurt other people Becomes a complicated thing. Because no few people are adamant that his deeds Correct or forced to guard prestige than confess error. Firth (1935) suggests that there is a relationship between pragmatics and speech acts (speech acts) is very close because speech acts are the center of pragmatics (in Djajasudarma, 2012:26). Firth who was the first linguist also proposed to conduct a discourse study to see his ideas that the context of the situation needs to be studied by linguists because they study language and work language considers the context of the situation (in Djajasudarma, 2012:60).

Using Olshtain and Cohen's taxonomy (1983), Nikmah (2012) analyzed the apology expressions of the characters of the film "Twilight". inside the 22 instances of apologizing acts in the movie, characters made use of 3 strategies of Expression of remorse, the offer of apology, and clarification. concerning elements figuring out the choice of apology strategies, diploma of the offense, context, social popularity and the connection among characters were the vastest ones.

Given the advent above, it can to be said that apology as one of the most critical speech acts has been broadly investigated up to now. but, its potential for language teaching/getting to know functions has now not been touched upon thoroughly. Taking a corpus-based approach, this has a look at examined apology expressions in an English sitcom and analyzed them in phrases of the types of apology strategies used by the characters involved, the varieties of offenses triggering using apology strategies, and factors affecting the choice of apology strategies. Having executed so, it sought to shed light on the implications of apologies for language coaching and language getting to know.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

Making a research design is a crucial stage in conducting research. A technique to accomplish stated research objectives, research design acts as a guide or mentor for researchers throughout the research process (Nursalam, 2003). The same was said by Sarwono. According to Sarwono (2006), a research design serves as a road map for researchers, guiding and determining the direction of the research process accurately and precisely in accordance with the goals established. Without the proper design, a researcher will be unable to conduct research properly because the person in question lacks clear directions.

This study's methodology is a qualitative one. Using qualitative techniques more detailed and in-depth, the results of the research can describe a realistic view of the social world that has been experienced by the informants. According to Moleong (2017: 6), qualitative research is research that is intended to understand phenomena about what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, perceptions, motivations, actions, and others holistically and using descriptions in the form of words and language, in a special natural context by utilizing various natural methods. Qualitative research according to Hendryadi (2019: 218) is a naturalistic inquiry process that seeks an in-depth understanding of natural social phenomena.

The Research instrument is the method used to measure and collect data. The research instrument is very important because it can affect the validity of the data used in research. Sumadi Sugiyono (2006:102), a research instrument is

a tool used to measure observed natural and social events (research variables). according to Sanjaya (2011: 84), a research instrument is a tool that can be used to collect research data or information. This data collection instrument was carried out so that the research was more systematic and easier. In this study, researchers will use interview tests to ask participants and to find out how they apologize in English and Indonesian. then the researcher will include the results of their interviews in written form. The main instrument in this research is the interview test instrument, while other instruments are complementary to support the data.

Margono (2007), Essentially perception methods are utilized to see and notice changes in friendly peculiarities that develop and foster which can then be made changes to these appraisals, so that eyewitnesses might see objects at certain moments, so they can combine what is needed and what is not needed. Obtaining information through verbal inquiries and responses is known as an interview or deliberation. The information that is gathered can be written down or recorded as audio, video, or audio-visual. S. Margono (2000:159) says that interviews are a way to get information by asking questions that need to be answered verbally. The most important aspect of the interview is that both the information seeker and the source of the information are present in person.

Documentation Methods

In this study, the documentation method was used as evidence of accurate data related to document information. According to Margono (2005:158) "Documentation is a method for gathering information from written sources, such as archives and books on opinions, propositional theories, laws, and other topics related to research issues.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This part of data presentation is still related to the previous chapter. These findings are analyzed and described and then discussed in this chapter to obtain the results of this study. The following observations, interviews, and documentation that have been carried out by the research studies show the following: Students' knowledge and Ability regarding apologies. In this way, the researcher conducted observations and interviews related to this research problem. Researchers focus on students in Muhammadiyah boarding school Rappang with 2 students from class VII, 2 students from class VIII, 2 students from class IX as research subjects. Researchers collect data with structural interview systematically by collecting data based on what researchers see or hear from respondents.

This section presents a discussion of the research results. The discussion is focused on the findings of the problem formulation. The first discussion is about the Knowledge and Ability of Muhammadiyah boarding school Rappang students in apologizing and Muhammadiyah boarding school students' strategies in apologizing as well as interviews with English and Indonesian teachers to find out the problems of students around the school as well as cases

and ways students apologize from the teacher's point of view and also want to know the extent of the teacher's knowledge about apologies.

In this session, the researcher wanted to discuss how cases of apologies and disputes between students in the school environment from the perspective of the teachers, as well as the actions they take if there are students who have disputes and are reluctant to apologize. According to interviews conducted by researchers to English and Indonesian language teachers. Both of them admitted that disputes often occur in the school environment, be it small disputes such as disagreements, disputes while playing and arguing. Up to major disputes such as mocking each other and even bullying.

As a teacher, of course, there are actions taken so that disputes between students in the boarding school environment can be resolved. The action taken by the first respondent if the dispute occurs because of different opinions, she will straighten out the student's difference of opinion. But if the dispute occurs because of fighting while playing, she will first find out the student's problem and provide the best solution. Unlike the first respondent, the action taken by the second respondent is to try to make the students who have disputes immediately make up and advise them not to make any more mistakes that can cause the dispute.

Children who do not apologize are often considered disrespectful and disrespectful to others. However, according to the first respondent, usually children who do not want to apologize because they feel they are right. So according to her, what she will do when this happens to her students, she will first trace who is right and who is wrong. because automatically if she has found out who is guilty, then the child will apologize. while what the second respondent will do is call both of them and advise that the action (reluctant to apologize) is wrong and we should apologize if we are wrong.

CONCLUSION

Based on the statements given, we can conclude that apologizing can show that we are sorry for doing something. By apologizing, we can also remember the actions that we should no longer do. If our actions turn out to hurt others, we must immediately apologize for the relationship not to be tenuous, not to hate each other, not to hurt each other and other negative things. Both with parents, family, teachers, friends, and society. Admitting a mistake and apologizing is not an easy thing to do. Not a few people are prestigious and have high egos to apologize first. However, this must be done in order to maintain harmony and cohesiveness. Based on researcher observations and interviews from students at the boarding school, several ways to apologize to friends that can be done are taking responsibility for mistakes, realizing religious teachings and values, finding the right time to apologize, not blaming others, and promising to change attitudes for the better.

The speech act of apologizing is an expressive speech act that functions to maintain harmony between speakers and speakers. The speech act of apologizing is closely related to aspects of politeness so it is necessary to pay attention to the strategies used. The strategy chosen must also reflect the true feelings so that the effect of the apology is conveyed. There are 5 strategies for apologizing: The expression of apology directly, apology by giving an explanation, apology by saying responsibility, apology by offering improvements and apology by promising not to repeat it again.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For students, knowing what they did wrong when apologizing. do not let students apologize because they are afraid of their friends. It is important for students to be able to reflect on themselves after making mistakes so that they do not repeat them again. For schools, it is important to improve character learning to improve the culture of manners in the school environment, especially for students. The researcher realizes, although in this writing has tried as much as possible, but in writing this thesis it cannot be separated from mistakes and errors. Therefore, the researcher really hopes for criticism and suggestions from various parties for future improvements.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Apologizing in English and Indonesian : An Interlanguage Pragmatic Case Study of Students at Muhammadiyah Boarding School Rappang."

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